

On the Study of Tetrahydrated Double Sulphate of Tervalent Elements with Radioactive Indicators. Part I

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Study of the tetrahydrated double sulphate of composition, $R.M(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, where R stands for alkali metals and M for trivalent element, is not complete probably because of simultaneous existence of products with different composition.

Distribution studies with $(NH_4)Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ as host and Y^{91} and $Eu^{152,154}$ as guests show that distribution factors have constant values both at tracer scale and in finite concentrations of the guest ions, thus providing a convincing evidence that tetrahydrated double sulphates of yttrium and europium like that of cerium do also exist. That diffusion in the crystal of the host lattice is a very slow process has been demonstrated by a study of the rate of uptake of Ce^{144} (ous) by preformed $(NH_4)Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ crystals in contact with its saturated solution in $3N-H_2SO_4$.

Unlike most of the trivalent elements, those with comparatively large ionic radius fail to form any alum. Indium rather serves as a limiting element to form alum, where ammonium, rubidium, and cesium alums only are known. Any attempt to prepare sodium or potassium indium alum results in the formation of $R.In(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, where R stands for Na or K. Existence of potassium indium alum has, however, been demonstrated through radioactive tracers^{1,2} and that of ammonium thallic alum has been shown through overgrowth³, although none of them have yet been isolated, due probably to their unstable nature and high solubility.

Next well-known hydrated double sulphate of trivalent elements is the tetrahydrated double sulphate. Formation of this series has been claimed not only in case of aluminium, iron, and thallium, but it also covers in a scattered way most of the trivalent elements including some of the rare earths. Even morphological analogy was envisaged by Fortini and Piccini³ on the study of overgrowth of $(NH_4)Al(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ on $(NH_4)Tl(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$. Though claims on the existence and preparation of some of the tetrahydrated double sulphates have been made, the full series has not yet been worked out. It is, however, expected that these should be morphologically analogous though very little attempt has been made to show the analogy. Difficulties of the earlier workers as regards isolation were probably due to simultaneous existence of different complex sulphates and hydrates. Application of radioactive indicators and the distribution study with selected host lattices, like $(NH_4)Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, may selectively pick up the guest and demonstrate the existence of tetrahydrated double sulphates of trivalent elements, where these are unknown, and in case of a known system such a study will establish morphological relations, if there is any.

1. Purkayastha and Das, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 163.

2. Purkayastha and Dutta this *issue*, p. 879.

3. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, 31, 451.

With these objects in view, the distribution studies with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and radioactive isotopes of different trivalent elements as guests have been undertaken. Present study, however, deals with demonstrating the existence of tetrahydrated double sulphates of europium and yttrium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ceric sulphate and ammonium sulphate used in the investigation were of E. Merck G.R. quality. B. D. H., AnalaR sulphuric acid was used throughout. Yttrium oxide was of spec. pure quality, supplied by Messrs. Johnson Matthey, England. Y^{91} was supplied by Messrs. Philips Duphar. $\text{Eu}^{152,154}$ was procured from A.E.R.E. Harwell, England. Both europium and yttrium in tracer scale were in the form of chlorides in HCl. A few drops from the stock were taken in H_2SO_4 (1N) and the tracer study was carried out with this secondary stock solution. In case of finite quantities, which was done in the case of yttrium, the following procedure was adopted to ensure thorough exchange between the tracer and the bulk of inactive yttrium. Tracer yttrium from the stock solution was added to a solution of the yttrium oxide, dissolved in HCl. It was then stirred and precipitated with gaseous ammonia. The precipitate was redissolved and reprecipitated with gaseous ammonia. The hydroxide was washed with warm water till free of chloride and dissolved in $3N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

To prepare a stock solution of cerous sulphate, ceric sulphate, dissolved in H_2SO_4 , was reduced to cerous state by H_2O_2 . Excess of H_2O_2 was decomposed by boiling and the volume was adjusted to 3N with respect to H_2SO_4 . Concentration of the solution was ascertained by estimating cerium as CeO_2 .

A preliminary examination showed that when 4.6g. of ammonium sulphate was added to a 50-ml solution of cerous sulphate ($1.4 \times 10^{-1}M$), crystals appeared after sometime. These were filtered, washed with cold $3N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and then with absolute ethanol, and dried by pressing between filter papers. Analysis of the product conformed to the composition $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The procedure for crystallising different fractions was the same as adopted in another communication¹.

Solid ammonium sulphate was taken in the horizontal portion of the tube. Cerous sulphate from the stock solution was then added and the activity was also added simultaneously. Variation in the extent of crystallisation was made by adding different quantities of $3N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. It should be noted that the solid phase does not crystallise easily unless there is a high degree of supersaturation. Supersaturation in such cases was broken by addition of freshly prepared $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals. A fraction of the solution was then pipetted out through filter paper cap, tied at the mouth of the delivery end, and activity and cerium left in the solution were ascertained. From the knowledge of the amount of cerium and activity, left in the solution, the extent of solid separated and the activity co-separated were computed. As a known volume was taken, filtration and washing were thus avoided. The activity remaining in the solution was measured by a liquid counter and the homogene-

ous and heterogeneous distribution factors, D and λ , were calculated from the following expressions:

$$D = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{tracer}}{\text{carrier}}\right)_{\text{solid}}}{\left(\frac{\text{tracer}}{\text{carrier}}\right)_{\text{soln.}}}; \quad \lambda = \frac{\log \frac{\text{initial tracer}}{\text{tracer in solution}}}{\log \frac{\text{initial carrier}}{\text{carrier in solution}}}$$

Results are recorded in the tables and in Figs. 1-3.

In view of the fact that the host lattice crystallises slowly from a supersaturated solution, we had to find out the minimum time required for complete breakdown of supersaturation which was necessary for computing heterogeneous distribution coefficient. We chose the solution having the lowest degree of supersaturation in our investigation. Cerous sulphate in 3*N*-H₂SO₄ together with ammonium sulphate was taken in a series of tubes. Supersaturation was broken down, as already mentioned, and the tubes were shaken in the thermostat. Cerium was estimated at frequent intervals. Complete breakdown of supersaturation took about 20 hours (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1. Extent of crystallisation of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with respect to time from a supersaturated solution of components in question in 3*N*-H₂SO₄ at 20°, showing the time required for complete breakdown of supersaturation.

In the series of experiments with preformed precipitate, solid $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared in the way already described. Crystals, so obtained, were dried at the room temperature, powdered, and filtered through 150 mesh. The desired activity was added to a saturated solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 3*N*-H₂SO₄. Aliquot portions of this solution were taken in a series of tubes, as described previously, and the weighed amount of powdered solid was added to each. The tubes were then shaken in a thermostat at the desired temperature. The variation of temperature was within $\pm 0.5^\circ$.

To find out the minimum time required for the attainment of equilibrium, the same quantity of powdered solid was taken in a definite volume of saturated solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 3*N*-H₂SO₄ in a series of tubes, as was done by Khlopin and Marculova⁴. The activity was then added and the tubes were shaken in the thermostat. The extent of uptake was measured at intervals of time. Minimum time required for the apparent attainment of equilibrium is about 4 days (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2. Distribution of Y⁹¹(A) and Ce¹¹⁴(B) between $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals and its saturated solution in about 3*N*-H₂SO₄ medium at 20°, showing the attainment of equilibrium.

N.B.—Initial yttrium ion conc. was 1×10^{-3} molar. Cerous ion conc. was $1.4 \times 10^{-1} M$ in both the cases. Guest cerium in case of (B) was of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$. —Left hand side scale. . . . Right hand side scale.

In order to determine D , we varied the solid surface. These in contact with saturated solutions of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in $3N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ were shaken for 5 days for the attainment of equilibrium. The activity and cerium concentration of the solution were then measured and D was computed. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE I
Co-precipitation of Y^{91} , $\text{Eu}^{152,154}$ and Ce^{144} with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$
in $3N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ medium.

Time since the appearance of the solid phase.	Initial tracer conc.	Temp.	% Ce. pptd.	% Tracer pptd.	D .	λ .
	A. Conc. of Y.					
20 hr.	$3 \times 10^{-7} M$	20°	74.7	17.0	0.971	0.137
			68.7	14.3	0.983	0.140
			58.6	12.7	0.103	0.154
			43.9	9.6	0.135	0.174
					Av. 0.156	
2½ days	3×10^{-7}	20°	75.6	17.8	0.969	0.139
			68.6	15.9	0.997	0.151
			60.4	13.6	0.156	0.156
			51.3	12.1	0.130	0.179
					Av. 0.156	
20 hr.	1×10^{-2}	20°	74.4	16.8	0.969	0.135
			66.8	14.5	0.983	0.142
			58.9	12.6	0.108	0.151
			43.9	9.3	0.131	0.141
					Av. 0.144	
6 days	"	20°	77.6	20.5	0.074	0.153
			70.4	16.5	0.083	0.148
			61.3	13.4	0.098	0.152
			52.7	10.6	0.106	0.149
					Av. 0.150	
5 "	"	15°	79.4	20.0	0.064	0.141
			72.3	16.4	0.075	0.139
			60.8	12.6	0.073	0.154
			55.5	8.8	0.077	0.113
					Av. 0.129	
"	"	5°	82.3	20.6	0.055	0.133
			77.0	18.0	0.065	0.135
			67.2	14.6	0.083	0.141
			62.6	11.3	0.076	0.123
					Av. 0.123	
	B. Conc. of Eu.					
20 hr.	$9 \times 10^{-7} M$	20°	78.1	62.8	0.473	0.651
			70.4	54.1	0.490	0.639
			61.4	44.7	0.500	0.623
			51.7	39.0	0.590	0.638
					Av. 0.646	
	C. Conc. of Ce.					
"	1.76×10^{-3}	20°	73.3	76.4		1.09
			65.8	68.3		1.07
			55.9	58.3		1.06
			41.0	44.0		1.10
					Av. 1.06	

N. B. 495 mg. of cerium in 50 ml and 4.62 g. of solid ammonium sulphate were taken in tubes already described. Extent of crystallisation of the solid phase was varied, as described previously, by adding different quantities of $3N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

TABLE II

Distribution of Y⁹¹ and Eu¹⁵²⁻¹⁵⁴ between preformed (NH₄)₂ Ce(SO₄)₂ · 4H₂O crystals and its saturated solution in 3N-H₂SO₄ medium at 20°.

Time of shaking.	Cerium in solid phase.	Tracer (Y ⁹¹ and Eu ¹⁵²⁻¹⁵⁴ in solid phase).	D.
Initial Y conc. = 1 × 10 ⁻² M.			
5 days	78.6%	13.4%	0.041
	74.0	11.4	0.048
	64.8	8.1	0.048
	55.0	5.5	0.047
	50.1	4.5	0.047
			Av. 0.048
Initial Eu conc. = 9.0 × 10 ⁻⁷ M.			
6	80.4	56.9	0.321
	60.4	29.1	0.269
	40.6	17.5	0.306
	23.0	7.8	0.283
			Av. 0.295

TABLE III

Attainment of equilibrium on the uptake of Y⁹¹ with interanally co-precipitated guest lattice along with cerous ammonium sulphate tetrahydrate in 3N-H₂SO₄ at 20°.

Initial Y conc. = 1 × 10 ⁻² M.							
Time.	Carrier pptd.	Uptake.	λ.	Time.	Carrier pptd.	Uptake.	λ.
2 hr.	71.6%	14.5%	0.122	25 hr.	79.5%	18.4%	0.128
4	73.6	15.6	0.127	44	82.2	18.6	0.120
9	74.6	15.0	0.118	65	80.5	18.7	0.126
16	78.2	16.8	0.120	88	79.5	18.5	0.128
20	78.9	16.4	0.122				

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that heterogeneous distribution factors (λ) are constant within experimental limitations. Because of low partition values in the case of yttrium, we had to take a large number of data to verify the constancy under different experimental conditions (both at tracer and finite concentrations). The constancy of λ leads to the conclusion that yttrium and europium are taken up by the host lattice through mixed crystal formation. From the consideration of the valency and analogy of the elements with cerous cerium, it can be inferred that the corresponding compounds of yttrium and europium also do exist.

Incidentally, though tetrahydrated double sulphate of europium has not been isolated as yet, the analogy of the rare earths amongst themselves leads to the expectation that europium may also form a double salt, analogous in composition to that of cerous cerium.

In case of yttrium earlier literature⁵, however, reveals that there is a double sulphate having composition like $2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{Y}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Our study evidently shows that tetrahydrated double sulphate of yttrium should also exist. Failure in the isolation of these compounds in case of yttrium and europium may possibly be due to the simultaneous existence of other hydrates or sulphates of different compositions of these two elements (*vide supra*).

Fig. 3, where λ values have been plotted against ionic radii, shows that λ values fall in a smooth straight line, which is characteristic of double salt in case of rare earths provided

FIG. 3. Relation of λ values with reference to ionic radii in the distribution of Y^{90} and $\text{Eu}^{152,154}$ as guests and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host. λ in case of cerium has been taken as unity.

of diffusion and recrystallisation in the system (specially with yttrium) being a very slow process. This phenomenon even in internally formed systems may be visualised on studying the negligible change in partition values (Table III), determined at intervals, keeping the extent of crystallisation near about the same.

The study in internally formed system was conducted with yttrium as guest and cerous cerium as host where there was considerable difference in size of their ions. It was therefore decided that the attainment of equilibrium should be studied with $\text{Ce}(\text{III})$ as guest and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals as host and compared with that of yttrium in externally formed system under identical conditions. Fig. 2 shows that equilibrium between the host and guest (in case of yttrium) is reached in about 4 days. In case of $\text{Ce}(\text{III})$ as guest, uptake follows a steep course at the beginning and after 4 days, the rate of uptake falls considerably, but it always follows an increasing trend and at the end of about 11 days, we get a D value of 0.5 in place of unity. If the same guest ion takes so much time in exchange through diffusion and recrystallisation, it will not be very much surprising in case of yttrium to obtain a much lower rate of exchange where there is difference in ionic size and in other properties as well. The comparatively flat portion in case of yttrium after a steep rise may therefore be regarded as an attainment of adsorption equilibrium. As greater

5. Vickery, "Chemistry of Lanthanones," Academic Press Inc., New York, 1953, p. 90.

6. Gordon and Rowley. *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29; 34.

variation in surfaces could not be achieved, the apparent constancy of D , as shown in Table II, cannot have any significance. The uptake, as it is expected, follows, however, an adsorption isotherm. Such a flat portion may be due to a very slow process of exchange through diffusion and recrystallisation. This is the reason why after equilibration of five days, D values in case of both yttrium and europium are much lower in magnitude than the λ values.

Question naturally arises whether the slow rate of attainment of equilibrium in the externally formed system in case of cerium as guest is due to any solution complexities of Ce(III) at such a low concentration. The particular issue was eliminated by preparing the guest ion having the same concentration both in internally and externally formed systems. Carrier-free cerium was added to a finite amount of cerium and precipitation was made by ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide to ensure thorough exchange. It was then dissolved in H_2SO_4 (dil.) and the procedure was repeated. Final guest-ion concentration in the medium was $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ ($\sim$). Table I (Ce(III)) shows that λ values are constant and unity. The slow rate of exchange in externally formed system with cerous ion as guest cannot therefore be regarded as due to any complexities in the solution of Ce(III) at such a low concentration, as mentioned above. It rather supports the earlier observation⁷ that in well-formed crystals, extent of recrystallisation is negligibly small. It should also be noted that even in radium-barium bromide system⁸, it requires about 12 days for attainment of equilibrium in externally formed system where the host lattice is highly soluble and partition factor is also very high ($D=10$).

Though convincing evidence has been put forth in favour of the behaviour that we have observed as regards great difference in the study of heterogeneous distribution factor, λ , and homogeneous distribution factor (D), yet morphological change of the host lattice just after its crystallisation requires further observation. It may so happen that the host lattice during crystallisation may crystallise with different molecules of water which ultimately change into tetrahydrate. We analysed the solid phase in contact with solution at different intervals of time, namely, after 1 hour, 1, 4, and 5 days since the appearance of the first crystals. We found that the composition to be that of a tetrahydrate. We powdered the freshly prepared solid phase, kept it at room temperature (30°), and analysed the product after 2 days and 3 days. Here also analytical data correspond to the formula of a tetrahydrate. From such study it can be inferred that no hydrate other than the tetrahydrate is formed during our investigation. The crystals at the time of first appearance are, however, beyond the range of chemical study. Since λ values, computed just after breakdown of supersaturation, are the same as had been seen even after shaking for a period of 6 days, it is only reasonable to assume that the crystals do not undergo any morphological change even after their first appearance.

From the facts stated above, it seems that the study of heterogeneous distribution factor, λ , is less time-consuming and homogeneous distribution factor, D , may sometimes lead to anomalous findings unless a thorough study is made as regards attainment of equilibrium.

7. Hahn, "Applied Radiochemistry", Cornell University Press, New York, 1936, pp. 74-75.

8. Seaborg and Katz, "The Actinide Elements", 1954, p. 775.

9. Wahl and Bonner, "Radioactivity Applied to Chemistry", John Wiley, New York, 1951, pp. 108-112.

Incidentally, the solubility of the host lattice is, however, low. It will be much more convenient to deal with the host lattice with high solubility to bring in all the trivalent elements in the field of our study.

It is interesting to point out that radioactive isotopes, as has been demonstrated here, can be used in search of morphologically analogous interesting compounds which have not yet been described because of the difficulty in finding out experimental conditions that can sort out the desired product.

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